

EMOTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE

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Abstract: The article shows the development of emotional characteristics of children of primary school age. The development of intellectual feelings of students in the learning process, children are faced with a large amount of knowledge and facts in educational activities, create feelings of surprise, uncertainty, joy in children, creating the basis for the formation of curiosity, inquisitiveness and other similar feelings.

Keywords: primary school age, children, emotional, characteristics, development, intellectual, cognitive process, educational activity, knowledge, feelings, formation.

INTRODUCTION

We must always remember that the future of our country depends on how the younger generation will be brought up, with what spiritual qualities it will grow up, how active our children will be in life, what high goals they will serve, and we must always care and fight for the comprehensive spiritual development of our children, for their spiritual and moral maturity, for their physical health. The future begins today. If we do not pay attention to the issue of education now, the future will be lost. Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and other truly human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything. Teachers are responsible for the upbringing and education of the mature generation in all respects.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Feelings of primary school children differ from feelings of preschoolers in that they are much more stable and conscious, these feelings pass more calmly, remain much deeper and stronger. In the general emotional tone of primary school students, a mood of cheerfulness and spiritual freshness prevails. They are cheerful and lively in lessons and during games during breaks. This situation is considered the norm in the emotional life of primary school students. The emotional life of primary school children significantly expands under the influence of education and upbringing. Unlike the feelings of preschoolers, in the primary school period there is a greater differentiation in the direction of feelings. At this age, all types of higher feelings begin to develop. Feelings of primary school students manifest and develop in their activities. Primary school students can evaluate the results of each of their lessons. Evaluation can cause a person to feel satisfaction and dissatisfaction, which motivates the child to study well. Sometimes negative experiences caused by receiving low grades can deepen and become a character trait of the child due to the wrong reaction of the teacher and constant reprimands and criticism of adults. One of the main feelings that help primary school students get positive grades for their work is an intellectual feeling. Feelings associated with human mental activity are called intellectual feelings. Intellectual feelings include curiosity, feelings of surprise and amazement, feelings of trust, mistrust and doubt. Such emotions appear and are felt when various theoretical and practical questions arise, when solving problems and questions, when learning and learning something new. Intellectual feelings of primary school students develop in the process of cognition. In educational activities, children encounter a large amount of knowledge and facts, they cause feelings of surprise, uncertainty, joy in children and form the basis for the formation of curiosity, inquisitiveness and other similar feelings. In the process of learning, as age and experience increase, a rational test develops. This feeling encourages a person to effectively engage in scientific research. Interest in learning is one of the characteristics of preschool children. Interest in learning takes on a

special direction in the primary school period. They look with surprise at everything they study.

A sense of surprise. In primary school children, such a feeling is born when they are affected by something unusual, unknown. Primary school students are surprised when unexpected events occur. In the process of learning, the feeling of surprise turns into joy. It is a constant companion of effective cognitive activity. "When we observe events, we are satisfied with the feelings that arise in us, and this satisfaction is intellectual joy (D. R. Descartes).

Surprise, born of something unexpected, makes primary school students take a closer look at things that at first glance seem unusual and out of the ordinary. Thus, surprise extremely motivates primary school students to learn about phenomena.

A sense of surprise. The feeling of surprise is strong in children of primary school age when they find it difficult to find the reasons for the new material being explained, the facts being studied, when they cannot include these facts in a group of previously known phenomena, and in such cases the child develops a feeling of surprise. This feeling is also a powerful means of further strengthening the cognitive activity of primary school students. A feeling of confidence. The correctness of the connections and relationships between things and events is determined in the process of thinking of primary school children, and in the presence of clear evidence in the practice itself with logically drawn conclusions, they develop a feeling of confidence. A feeling of doubt is not fully developed in primary school students, and this feeling is born when the child gradually comes into conflict with the rules or theories developed by him in the learning process and encounters them. This is a very important feeling, encouraging a thorough study of the collected evidence and the stated rules. "For effective scientific activity, it is necessary to always be skeptical and check yourself" (I. P. Pavlov). These feelings develop significantly when the child overcomes difficulties and achieves certain

successes in his work. A child of primary school age experiences great joy when learning to read and write, when learning to independently solve an example or problem. One of the main tasks of a primary school teacher is to ensure that students experience maximum joy from their work and turn it into the emotional side of the child's character.

CONCLUSION

In children of primary school age, intellectual and moral feelings, feelings of camaraderie and friendship begin to occupy a large place. Patriotism, a sense of conscious duty and similar feelings arise and grow. The development of moral feelings is influenced by

collective work, the content of studies, various public organizations and, of course, the personal example of the teacher. At the beginning of training, it is the personality of the teacher that determines the development of many moral feelings of a primary school student. At first, the student is connected with the class collective only through his teacher. The teacher is the central figure to whom all the child's attention and feelings are concentrated. A knowledgeable, skillful, loving teacher maintains such an attitude of his students even at the later stages of training. But later this love, affection is divided between the teacher and the class collective, comrades, friends. However, for a primary school student, the main authority is the teacher. At home, he speaks of his teacher with love and respect.

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